

Implementation of Cryptographic Approach for Image Transmission with Security

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Abstract--- In this paper an approach for secured transmission of images and its implementation is being proposed. The proposed method proves to be better compared to various presently existing cryptographic algorithms. The basic application of this algorithm is to provide secured transmission of digital images for various multimedia usages. These encrypted messages can further be used for compact storage of information of patient details which are very much confidently for patient centric approach. The results of the implementation show that the computation time is faster comparatively and it is highly secured and also efficient method for image transmission. The input for demonstration is taken as Lena image on which the Elliptic Curve Cryptography method is applied. The major advantage of this approach is reduced key size.

Keywords--- ECC-Elliptic Curve Cryptography, Discrete Logarithm, Authenticity, Integrity.

I. Introduction

A lot of information is perceived when we observe an image. Images have become an inevitable source of information. Every day we come across various image from various sources. When images are confidential and we want the image to be transferred safe and securely, cryptography comes into play. The cryptographic technique which we have implemented in this paper is the Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC). Various study on ECC has concluded that the difficulty to solve an Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithmic Problem is exponentially hard with respect to the key size used. This property makes ECC a very good choice for encryption/decryption process compared to other cryptographic techniques which are linearly difficult or sub exponentially difficult. ECC is a public key cryptography which was developed by Neal Koblitz and Victor S. Miller independently in the year 1985. ECC gains wide acceptance around 2004. Elliptic curve cryptography (ECC), an approach based on the algebraic structure of elliptic curves over finite fields, is a public key cryptography that has attracted great attention in recent years. It offers security similar to traditional systems, such as rivest, Shamir, & Adleman (RSA), but with significantly smaller key lengths [1]. For example, 163-bit ECC is considered equivalent to 1024-bit RSA [1, 2]. Thanks to this advantage, ECC can be implemented to strictly consider resource limitations. An elliptic curve E over a Galois field (GF) is the set of solutions to Eq. (1).

A point $P(xP, yP)$ is a pair of elements that satisfies.

$$y^2 + xy = x^3 + ax^2 + \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The underlying operation in ECCs is scalar point multiplication, $Q = kP$, the multiplication of an elliptic curve point P by a scalar k to give the resultant point Q [3] [4]. To perform this operation, the point addition and point doubling operations are combined effectively.

Three main steps to calculate the point multiplication are:

1. Convert point P from affine coordinate to project coordinate.
2. Compute $Q = kP$ as projective coordinate.
3. Convert point Q from projective coordinate to affine coordinate.

II. Related Work

The Image Based Encryption Technique [2] paper was a proposed method with statistical analysis, key sensitivity analysis and information entropy analysis to prove the existing method is secure against the most common attacks. First we define the histogram and the correlation of the two adjacent pixels in the image to prove the stability against statistical attacks. Second we define the key sensitivity analysis in the image to make brute force

attacks infeasible. Third we define the information entropy analysis in the image to protect the information in the encryption process. Then there is no unauthorized access of information in the encryption process. The image histogram shows the distribution of pixels in an image by plotting the number of pixels at each gray scale level we can say that histograms of the plain image and encrypted image are different to each other. The histogram of encrypted image is uniform. Thus, this histogram analysis is robust against statistical attacks. Correlation is defined as the relation of adjacent pixels in an image. Each pixel is highly correlated with its adjacent pixels either horizontally, vertically or diagonally. In a plain image correlation value is very close to 1, while in encrypted image its value should be as low as possible. Image Encryption using Different Techniques for High Security Transmission over a Network [3] paper proposes an idea where a single image can be split into n number of modules and they can be encrypted using suitable algorithms so that they can be securely transmitted in the form of shared image. Then in the next phase the split shared images are combined to form a single shared image and then decrypted. Securing Images using Encryption Techniques [1] paper proposes an idea where the password is given along with the input image. Value of each pixel of input image is converted into equivalent 8 bit binary number. Now length of password is considered for bit rotation and reversal. i.e., Number of bits to be rotated to left and reversed will be decided by the length of password. Since the weight of each pixel is responsible for its color the change occurred in the weight of each pixel of input image due to bits rotation reversal generates the encrypted image. Finally extended hill cipher is applied to make it more secure.

III. Literature Review

Darrel Hankerson, Alfred Menezes and Vanstone explained the various elliptic curve arithmetic, issue with implementation and cryptographic protocols in details¹. Lawrence C. Washington provided proofs to various theory related to elliptic curve². Jouko Teeriahho shows implementation of various aspect of ECC using Mathematica³. To securely transfer image across the network various techniques have been developed in recent years using ECC. Ahmed A, Abd El-Latif and XiamuNiu presented an image encryption technique using cyclic elliptic curve and chaotic system.

They proposed a technique to generate a pseudo random key stream using cyclic elliptic curve point and chaotic system which in turn is used for encryption of data stream from the image⁴.

Hong Liu and Yanbing Liu gave a cryptanalysis of image encryption scheme based on hybrid chaotic system and cyclic elliptic curve. They found that known-plain text attack and choosing a plain image with all the pixel value 0 can generate the encrypted image⁵.

S. Maria Celestin Vigila and K. Muneeswaran proposed an algorithm to perform image encryption using ECC⁶. They use a coupled Linear congruential generator to generate the private key and a random integer 'k'. To obtain the cipher image point multiplication is performed for each pixel value with the generator to fit into the elliptic curve coordinate. A mapping table is required while performing decryption. Ali Soleymani, Md Jan Nordin and Zulkarnain

Md Ali proposed an encryption technique using Elliptic Curve over Prime Group field⁷. They created a mapping table which has values of 0 to 163 along the row and the corresponding row contains the elliptic curve coordinate. Pixel value of the image are mapped onto elliptic curve coordinate using the table and encrypted using the public key of the receiver. To view the encrypted data as cipher image the table is used again to map the values back to the range of 0 to 163. S. Behnia, A. Akhavan, A. Akhshani, A. Samsudin proposed a novel image encryption algorithm using Jacobian elliptic map⁸.

They transform the plain image data matrix into one dimension matrix after operating with the key which is the initial condition and control parameters. Elements of the matrix are encrypted using an equation and matrix is reshaped back to original dimension. Li Li, Ahmed A. Abd El-Latif, XiamuNiu proposed an encryption scheme using Elliptic curve ElGamal based homomorphic image for sharing secret images.

They selected the parameter of the elliptic curve to resist Pollard's rho, isomorphic and Pohlig Hellman attack. The experimental result indicates that it is better than encryption using RSA and ElGamal. Don Johnson, Alfred Menezes and Scott Vanstone describe the implementation, related security and interoperability issue of Elliptic Curve Digital Signature

IV. Proposed Approach

The proposed method is implemented the image with Elliptic curve cryptography to provide security.

Figure 4.1: Block Diagram of Proposed Method

To decrease the number of computational steps in ECC operation, we perform two operations defined below.

4.1. Pixel Grouping Into a Single Integer

Images are made up of pixels. If cryptographic operation is performed on every single pixel it will take more time as the number of pixels present is very large. So, it will be a good option to group the pixels together. The number of pixels to be group depends on the Elliptic Curve parameters used. The larger the parameter of the elliptic curve, the more pixels can be grouped. For example a 512 bit ECC parameter can group upto 63 pixels together. To get the number of pixels to be group, find the number of the list, of the base 163 digits in the integer ‘ p ’ minus 1. To convert the group of pixels into a big single integer we have used a function of Mathematical called From Digits [list of pixels, b] which take a list of pixels and convert it to base b . We add random 1 or 2 to each pixel to avoid error caused while using From Digits function of Mathematical, in case, the first pixel value of the group is 0 and also to provide low correlated pixel value for the cipher image generated with same pixel value plain image. Pixel value of image in byte form will range from 0 to 163

4.2. Getting the Group of Pixels from the Big Integer

After the ECC operation the coordinate value will all be in the range of the bit size chosen for the ECC operation. To generate the cipher image from these coordinates we need to bring it down to 0 to 163 range. We performed using the Integer Digits [big integer value, 163] function in Mathematical. It takes as input the big integer values in the range of the size chosen for ECC operation and with base 163, the output will be a list of values ranging from 0 to 162.

The two functions, From Digits and Integer Digits are inverse of each other so the pixels value are preserved during the operation. Mathematical operation on an image is done on the pixels value of the image. So first, we get the pixels value of the image. The Elliptic curve parameters $\{a, b, G, p\}$ are agreed between the sender and the receiver. The sender uses the public key ‘ Pb ’ of the receiver to generate the cipher image from the pixels of the plain image. The receiver use the private key ‘ nB ’ which was used to generate the public key, to decrypt the cipher image back to the plain image.

4.3. Image Encryption

- a. Get the pixel value of the image to be encrypted and randomly add 1 or 2 to each pixel. Record the number of channels present in the image.
- b. Group the pixels and convert to single large integer value for each group. Number of pixel to be group using
- c. Mathematical is given by $grp = \text{Length} [\text{Integer Digits}[p, 168]] - 1$
- d. Pair up the result obtained from step 2 and store as ‘ Pm ’ which is the plain message input for the ECC system.
- e. Select a random ‘ k ’ and compute ‘ kG ’ and ‘ kPb ’ where ‘ Pb ’ is the public key of the receiver.
- f. Perform point addition of ‘ kPb ’ with each value of ‘ Pm ’ and store as ‘ Pc ’ which is the cipher text.
- g. Convert the cipher text list from step 5 to value ranging from 0 to 162.
- h. Pad left with 0 to each list from step 6 which have less than $grp + 1$ number of elements, to make each list equal in length.

- i. Flatten the list from step 7, group them according to the number of image channels that we have recorded and partition them to width of the plain image.
- j. Convert the values from step 8 into cipher image.

4.4. Image Decryption

- a. Get the pixel value of the cipher image and group by $grp+ 1$ number of pixels and form single big integer value for each group with base 163. Record the number of image channels of the cipher image.
- b. Pair up the value obtained from step 1.
- c. Perform point multiplication of 'kG' with 'nB' where 'nB' is the private key of the receiver.
- d. Perform point subtraction between values from step 2 with value from step 3.
- e. Get the value in the range of 0 to 162 from step 4 with base 258 and subtract random 2 from each value.
- f. Group the flatten value obtained in step 5 in term of recorded number of image channels of the cipher image and partition them to the width of the cipher image.
- g. Convert the values from step 6 into plain image.

V. Implementation of ECC

Point multiplication is the heart of ECC having high speed which is defined in to two distinct layers.

- a) Point multiplication
- b) Point addition and Doubling

The Architecture of ECC is shown below

Figure 5.1: Architecture of ECC

The scalar multiplication is found out by P is added k times to itself. Which involves the four different layers.

- a) Addition
- b) Multiplication
- c) Squaring
- d) Division/inversion

A polynomial representation based on the irreducible polynomial $f(x)=x^{163}+x^7+x6+x^3+1$ will be used.

Point addition: Let $P = (x1, y1)$ belongs to $E (F2^m)$ and $Q= (x2, y2)$ belongs to $E (F2^m)$, where P not equal to Q . Then $P + Q = (x3, y3)$, where $x3 = \lambda^2 + \lambda + x1 + x2 + a$ and

$y3 = \lambda(x1 + x3) + x3 + y1$ with $\lambda = (y1 + y2)/(x1 + x2)$. Point doubling: Let $P = (x1, y1)$ belongs to $E (F2^m)$, where $P = -P$. Then $2P = (x3, y3)$, and $x3 = \lambda^2 + \lambda + a = x12 + b/x12$ and $y3 = x12 + \lambda x3 + x3$ with $\lambda = x1 + y1/x1$.

Figure 5.2: Point Addition Operation

Figure 5.3: Block Diagram for Point Addition Operation

5.1. Point Multiplication

Point Multiplication is the basis of ECC Processor. All the finite field arithmetic, point addition and doubling constitutes the point multiplication. Montgomery point multiplication shows less delay, area and power [5]. Fig 5.4. Architecture for Point Multiplication

Fig. 5.4: Block Diagram for Point Multiplication

VI. Simulation Results

The following figure shows the result for the above inputs.

It is synthesized and simulated the architecture for a Xilinx XC3s500e-fg320 FPGA, using the ISE 9.2i. Simulation results by using ISim Simulator for *point multiplication* are shown as waveform. Here design has been tested for 233-key bits length. The output obtained at 1000ns with a key bit length is 233-bit. finally the goal is Optimization Speed that is Minimum period: 26.017ns (Maximum Frequency: 38.436MHz) and Minimum input arrival time before clock: 4.510ns, Maximum output required time after clock: 10.699ns. Total memory usage is 563960 kilobytes.

Figure 6.1: Point Multiplication is Shown as Waveform. Here Design has been Tested for 233-key bits Length Device Utilization Summary

Table 1: Device Utilization Summary

Number of Slices	18163 out of 4656 390% (*)
Number of Slice Flip Flops	86 out of 9312 0%
Number of 4 input LUTs	36395 out of 9312 390% (*)
Number used as logic	34997
Number used as RAMs	1398
Number of IOs	501
Number of bonded IOBs	501 out of 232 215% (*)
Number of GCLKs	1 out of 24 4%

Timing Summary

Speed Grade: -5

Table 2: Timing Summary

Minimum period	26.017ns (Maximum Frequency: 38.436MHz)
Minimum input arrival time before clock	4.510ns
Maximum output required time after clock	10.699ns
Maximum combinational path delay	8.842ns
Total memory usage is 563960 kilobytes.	

VII. Conclusion

In this paper a new mapping method introduced to convert an image pixel value to a point on a predefined elliptic curve over finite field GF (p) using a map table. This mapping technique is very fast with low complexity and computation, easy to implement and for low entropy plain images, mapping will results a high distribution of different points for repetitive intensity values. Creating this map table is completely explained with a simple elliptic curve function as an example. Encryption and decryption process implemented and tested on Lena image. Encryption and decryption results are mentioned. All statistical analyses are performed on encrypted imaged to

evaluate the strength of this algorithm. Respect to histogram, correlation, entropy and key sensitivity analysis, this cryptosystem provides a reliable security for transmitting images over public channels. As a future work, this method could be combined with a chaos map to achieve hybrid cryptography with more diffusion and confusion with respect to running time.

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